

Brightness Temperature Comparison of Enhanced Resolution SSMIS T_B Images Created from CSU ICDR V1 and GPM L1C V5 Files

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Abstract

The Calibrated Enhanced Resolution Passive Microwave Daily Equal-Area Scalable Earth (EASE) Grid 2.0 Brightness Temperature (CETB) Earth System Data Record (ESDR) project team has developed algorithms for creating Earth-based enhanced resolution brightness temperature (T_B) images from swath-based CSU FCDR files. In this report, these algorithms are applied to CSU ICDR and GPM L1C files and the relative T_B values. It is found that there are noisy differences that appear correlated with the surface type. The channel dependent mean difference for either land or ocean varied from -0.60 K to 2.72 K while the standard deviations varied anywhere from 0.21 K to 7.11 K for EASE2_T. Looking at an average mean and average std for assessing passes for horizontally polarized 37 GHz of EASE2_T, the overall mean difference is 1.09 K (land), and 1.39 K (ocean) with a std of 1.23 K (land), and 1.04 K (ocean). Similar statistics exist for EASE2_N and EASE2_S.

1 Introduction

The NASA MEaSUREs Calibrated Enhanced Resolution Passive Microwave Daily EASE-Grid 2.0 Brightness Temperature ESDR (CETB) Earth System Data Record (ESDR)[1] is produced from the Colorado State University (CSU) Fundamental Climate Data Record (CSU FCDR V1) [2]. The data producers used the same software system to produce an interim version of the data, produced and distributed in near real-time as the Interim Climate Data Record (CSU ICDR V1). Both FCDR and ICDR use the DMSP F13 SSM/I as the cross-calibration sensor. The GPM Level 1C (L1C V5) brightness temperatures (T_B) are produced by the NASA Precipitation Precipitation System (PPS) [3] using the Global Precipitation Mission (GPM) microwave imager (GMI) as the cross-calibration sensor.

The purpose of this report is to compare gridded T_B differences between the two different data sources (CSU ICDR V1 and GPM L1C V5). The method used is to compute daily gridded CETB images from both sensors separately for each channel and local time of day (ltod). The

difference of the images created from each data source are computed and analyzed. Figures 2-57 present the EASE2_T difference images for the selected days (Days 01, 101, 201, and 301 for 2019). Figures 58-113 present the EASE2_N difference images for the same selected days. Figures 114-169 present the EASE2_S difference images for the same selected days as EASE2_T and EASE2_N. The probability distribution of the difference values for EASE2_T, EASE2_N, and EASE2_S are also computed over a 10 day period (01-10, 101-110, 201-210, 301-310, 2019) and plotted in the same figures.

The mean differences appear to be consistent through the year within their channels. As the figures show, the mean difference varies with channel and local time of day (ltod), as does the standard deviation. Interestingly, the differences vary based on land or ocean surface. The largest differences lie around land ocean boundaries, which may be an artifact of resolution enhancements or possibly differences in geolocation. This is not an unexpected result when comparing land and ocean data together. The process of overlaying figures creates an imperfect overlap along the coastal edges, which can affect the data. However, there is a difference in when we compare land and ocean data separately, which we explore. Figure 1 shows the data results if we did not separate land and ocean.

To obtain more accurate results, we separated the land and ocean data using a sea/land mask[5]. The mask was made at Brigham Young University by plotting the 1987 CIA coastline database[6] into a map array image of $0.01^\circ \times 0.01^\circ$. Land areas of the map were then filled, creating a high resolution land mask. To create the land mask for any particular region, compute the latitude/longitude for each CETB pixel and compare it to the high resolution land mask, noting if the pixel center is land or ocean. Using this process, we compared land and ocean data individually. The separated results are then displayed together in the histograms. Data overlap is visible.

When comparing the data from EASE2_T, EASE2_N, and EASE2_S together, the results were relatively similar. The T_B differences in comparing L1C to I/FCDR over a global area and the Northern and Southern poles was fairly consistent. Land difference means for channels 37 V, 19 V, and 19 H are always negative for EASE2_T, EASE2_N, and EASE2_S. However, for the same channels the ocean difference means vary between positive and negative among the three sensors. Furthermore, EASE2_T, EASE2_N, and EASE2_S have multiple extreme standard deviations for channel 22 V. We conclude that the data derived from the two input sources differ significantly relative to one another. CETB images from the two sources should not be mixed in time series analysis.

2 Conclusion

This white paper considers the differences in gridded CETB images between two different data sources. A mean difference between data sets that depends on the channel (H or V) is noted, with differences somewhat dependent on surface type and location. Standard deviation also is dependent on the channel. However, the standard deviation appears to not be dependent on the direction or the season of year.

We conclude that CETB images derived from I/FCDR V1 and L1C V5 are significantly different. This is not surprising, given the differences in calibration cross-sensor (F13 vs. GPM)

and other details described in [2]. We recommend that data from the two different calibration methods should not be used interchangeably or for time series analysis. The differences between the two data sets are dependent on surface type, which is intriguing. The magnitude and sign of the differences are not consistent across all channels/pass directions.

3 References

References

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Table 1: Statistics of land and ocean differences(K) for EASE2_T over days 1-10, 2019.

channel	pass	land mean	ocean mean	land std	ocean std
19 H	A	1.41	1.65	0.88	1.63
19 H	D	1.44	1.74	0.57	0.57
19 V	A	1.28	1.90	5.78	3.08
19 V	D	1.53	1.89	0.64	2.59
22 V	A	2.37	2.54	5.94	0.29
22 V	D	2.47	2.53	0.24	0.21
37 H	A	1.09	1.40	0.73	0.61
37 H	D	1.13	1.39	0.59	0.54
37 V	A	-0.34	-0.37	0.44	0.32
37 V	D	-0.33	-0.37	0.31	0.28
91 H	A	-0.14	0.00	1.39	1.08
91 H	D	-0.11	-0.00	1.00	1.05
91 V	A	-0.45	-0.40	1.10	0.67
91 V	D	-0.42	-0.44	0.81	0.68

Table 2: Statistics of land and ocean differences(K) for EASE2_T over days 101-110, 2019.

channel	pass	land mean	ocean mean	land std	ocean std
19 H	A	1.43	1.75	1.05	0.86
19 H	D	1.44	1.75	0.59	0.49
19 V	A	1.45	2.06	0.66	0.51
19 V	D	1.48	2.06	0.37	0.32
22 V	A	2.41	2.53	0.50	0.41
22 V	D	2.43	2.53	0.26	0.24
37 H	A	1.04	1.40	0.85	0.78
37 H	D	1.09	1.38	0.63	0.59
37 V	A	-0.35	-0.36	0.49	0.41
37 V	D	-0.34	-0.37	0.35	0.30
91 H	A	-0.27	-0.00	1.26	1.10
91 H	D	-0.19	-0.01	1.05	1.02
91 V	A	-0.58	-0.43	1.03	0.64
91 V	D	-0.50	-0.43	0.83	0.65

Table 3: Statistics of land and ocean differences(K) for EASE2_T over days 201-210, 2019.

channel	pass	land mean	ocean mean	land std	ocean std
19 H	A	1.43	1.92	3.39	7.11
19 H	D	1.36	1.66	1.39	1.30
19 V	A	1.37	1.72	1.08	2.73
19 V	D	1.37	1.81	0.97	2.52
22 V	A	2.31	2.72	3.62	2.66
22 V	D	2.39	2.55	3.65	0.51
37 H	A	1.00	1.39	1.00	0.80
37 H	D	1.05	1.38	0.63	0.48
37 V	A	-0.35	-0.37	0.59	0.41
37 V	D	-0.35	-0.36	0.32	0.28
91 H	A	-0.38	-0.01	1.35	1.04
91 H	D	-0.33	-0.02	0.90	1.01
91 V	A	-0.54	-0.13	2.51	3.10
91 V	D	-0.60	-0.10	1.07	2.86

Table 4: Statistics of land and ocean differences(K) for EASE2_T over days 301-310, 2019.

channel	pass	land mean	ocean mean	land std	ocean std
19 H	A	1.45	1.74	0.87	0.40
19 H	D	1.43	1.75	0.54	0.35
19 V	A	1.47	2.05	0.48	0.30
19 V	D	1.49	2.05	0.34	0.26
22 V	A	2.37	2.53	4.25	0.19
22 V	D	2.44	2.54	0.27	0.74
37 H	A	1.04	1.39	0.69	0.45
37 H	D	1.09	1.39	0.60	0.46
37 V	A	-0.35	-0.37	0.38	0.25
37 V	D	-0.33	-0.36	0.31	0.24
91 H	A	-0.24	-0.00	1.20	0.90
91 H	D	-0.19	-0.00	0.94	1.01
91 V	A	-0.55	-0.43	0.96	0.57
91 V	D	-0.51	-0.42	0.68	0.65

Table 5: Average Probability distribution of differences for land and ocean over the four periods recorded for EASE2_T.

channel	pass	land mean	ocean mean	land std	ocean std
19 H	A	1.43	1.77	3.76	7.36
19 H	D	1.42	1.73	1.70	1.54
19 V	A	1.39	1.93	5.94	4.16
19 V	D	1.47	1.95	1.27	3.64
22 V	A	2.36	2.58	8.17	2.71
22 V	D	2.43	2.54	3.68	0.95
37 H	A	1.04	1.40	1.65	1.35
37 H	D	1.09	1.39	1.23	1.04
37 V	A	-0.35	-0.36	0.96	0.71
37 V	D	-0.34	-0.37	0.64	0.55
91 H	A	-0.26	-0.00	2.60	2.07
91 H	D	-0.21	-0.01	1.95	2.05
91 V	A	-0.53	-0.35	3.08	3.29
91 V	D	-0.51	-0.35	1.72	3.08

Table 6: Statistics of land and ocean differences(K) for EASE2_N over days 1-10, 2019.

channel	pass	land mean	ocean mean	land std	ocean std
19 H	M	1.44	1.71	0.65	0.60
19 H	E	1.43	1.68	0.91	1.04
19 V	M	1.58	1.85	0.74	2.79
19 V	E	1.29	1.90	6.35	3.91
22 V	M	2.50	2.53	0.25	0.23
22 V	E	2.49	2.53	0.38	0.37
37 H	M	1.17	1.37	0.57	0.56
37 H	E	1.13	1.38	0.70	0.65
37 V	M	-0.33	-0.37	0.31	0.29
37 V	E	-0.35	-0.36	0.40	0.34
91 H	M	-0.01	0.02	1.13	1.12
91 H	E	-0.05	-0.08	1.52	3.14
91 V	M	-0.30	-0.38	0.88	0.66
91 V	E	-0.34	-0.38	0.96	0.67

Table 7: Statistics of land and ocean differences(K) for EASE2_N over days 101-110, 2019.

channel	pass	land mean	ocean mean	land std	ocean std
19 H	M	1.45	1.72	0.63	0.48
19 H	E	1.43	1.72	1.16	1.14
19 V	M	1.53	2.01	0.40	0.35
19 V	E	1.49	2.01	0.71	0.66
22 V	M	2.46	2.54	0.29	0.21
22 V	E	2.44	2.54	0.55	0.49
37 H	M	1.13	1.37	0.63	0.53
37 H	E	1.07	1.39	0.88	0.95
37 V	M	-0.34	-0.36	0.36	0.28
37 V	E	-0.35	-0.36	0.50	0.51
91 H	M	-0.11	0.00	1.17	1.01
91 H	E	-0.20	0.01	1.29	1.13
91 V	M	-0.41	-0.41	0.94	0.64
91 V	E	-0.50	-0.41	1.02	0.68

Table 8: Statistics of land and ocean differences(K) for EASE2_N over days 201-210, 2019.

channel	pass	land mean	ocean mean	land std	ocean std
19 H	M	1.31	1.60	2.11	1.62
19 H	E	1.39	1.19	3.67	7.50
19 V	M	1.40	1.71	0.71	2.23
19 V	E	1.35	1.82	1.15	1.57
22 V	M	2.40	2.59	4.00	0.80
22 V	E	2.30	2.64	4.14	1.77
37 H	M	1.05	1.37	0.62	0.57
37 H	E	1.01	1.39	1.03	0.94
37 V	M	-0.35	-0.32	0.33	0.30
37 V	E	-0.35	-0.32	0.61	0.49
91 H	M	-0.32	-0.09	0.99	1.07
91 H	E	-0.36	-0.07	1.50	1.10
91 V	M	-0.61	-0.16	1.05	2.77
91 V	E	-0.48	-0.35	2.91	2.13

Table 9: Statistics of land and ocean differences(K) for EASE2_N over days 301-310, 2019.

channel	pass	land mean	ocean mean	land std	ocean std
19 H	M	1.45	1.74	0.87	0.40
19 H	E	1.43	1.75	0.54	0.35
19 V	M	1.47	2.05	0.48	0.30
19 V	E	1.49	2.05	0.34	0.26
22 V	M	2.37	2.53	4.25	0.19
22 V	E	2.44	2.54	0.27	0.74
37 H	M	1.04	1.39	0.69	0.45
37 H	E	1.09	1.39	0.60	0.46
37 V	M	-0.35	-0.37	0.38	0.25
37 V	E	-0.33	-0.36	0.31	0.24
91 H	M	-0.24	-0.00	1.20	0.90
91 H	E	-0.19	-0.00	0.94	1.01
91 V	M	-0.55	-0.43	0.96	0.57
91 V	E	-0.51	-0.42	0.68	0.65

Table 10: Average Probability distribution of differences for land and ocean over the four periods recorded for EASE2_N.

channel	pass	land mean	ocean mean	land std	ocean std
19 H	M	1.41	1.69	2.46	1.84
19 H	E	1.42	1.59	3.99	3.04
19 V	M	1.50	1.91	1.20	3.60
19 V	E	1.41	1.95	6.50	4.27
22 V	M	2.43	2.55	5.85	0.89
22 V	E	2.42	2.56	4.20	2.01
37 H	M	1.10	1.40	1.26	1.06
37 H	E	1.10	1.40	1.64	1.56
37 V	M	-0.34	-0.36	0.69	0.56
37 V	E	-0.35	-0.35	0.94	0.82
91 H	M	-0.17	-0.02	2.25	2.06
91 H	E	-0.20	-0.04	2.67	3.66
91 V	M	-0.47	-0.35	1.92	2.97
91 V	E	-0.46	-0.39	3.30	2.42

Table 11: Statistics of land and ocean differences(K) for EASE2_S over days 1-10, 2019.

channel	pass	land mean	ocean mean	land std	ocean std
19 H	M	1.39	1.73	0.90	0.89
19 H	E	1.31	1.62	1.16	1.92
19 V	M	1.53	1.91	0.73	2.35
19 V	E	1.51	1.88	0.94	2.13
22 V	M	2.42	2.53	0.25	0.22
22 V	E	2.20	2.54	9.35	0.23
37 H	M	1.12	1.39	0.65	0.59
37 H	E	1.09	1.40	0.70	0.56
37 V	M	-0.36	-0.37	0.34	0.30
37 V	E	-0.37	-0.37	0.44	0.30
91 H	M	-0.20	-0.00	0.99	1.15
91 H	E	-0.22	0.01	1.41	1.03
91 V	M	-0.50	-0.45	0.88	0.78
91 V	E	-0.50	-0.38	1.31	0.73

Table 12: Statistics of land and ocean differences(K) for EASE2_S over days 101-110, 2019.

channel	pass	land mean	ocean mean	land std	ocean std
19 H	M	1.47	1.75	0.66	0.40
19 H	E	1.46	1.76	0.68	0.40
19 V	M	1.61	2.07	0.48	0.28
19 V	E	1.60	2.07	0.52	0.29
22 V	M	2.42	2.53	0.24	0.17
22 V	E	2.41	2.53	0.27	0.19
37 H	M	1.15	1.38	0.66	0.48
37 H	E	1.12	1.39	0.67	0.48
37 V	M	-0.37	-0.37	0.33	0.25
37 V	E	-0.38	-0.37	0.35	0.25
91 H	M	-0.14	-0.00	0.95	1.11
91 H	E	-0.16	-0.00	1.26	1.06
91 V	M	-0.46	-0.41	0.73	0.68
91 V	E	-0.49	-0.41	1.08	0.63

Table 13: Statistics of land and ocean differences(K) for EASE2_S over days 201-210, 2019.

channel	pass	land mean	ocean mean	land std	ocean std
19 H	M	1.32	1.65	1.75	1.48
19 H	E	1.51	2.35	2.92	6.60
19 V	M	1.34	1.86	2.15	2.61
19 V	E	1.37	1.65	2.12	3.17
22 V	M	2.63	2.54	2.05	0.56
22 V	E	2.60	2.79	1.78	3.03
37 H	M	1.18	1.38	0.69	0.46
37 H	E	1.13	1.38	0.74	0.53
37 V	M	-0.37	-0.38	0.34	0.25
37 V	E	-0.39	-0.39	0.39	0.28
91 H	M	-0.08	0.05	0.97	1.11
91 H	E	-0.14	0.04	1.05	1.04
91 V	M	-0.05	-0.03	3.01	2.86
91 V	E	-0.14	0.04	2.69	3.50

Table 14: Statistics of land and ocean differences(K) for EASE2_S over days 301-310, 2019.

channel	pass	land mean	ocean mean	land std	ocean std
19 H	M	1.47	1.76	0.65	0.37
19 H	E	1.49	1.76	0.93	0.36
19 V	M	1.62	2.07	0.50	0.28
19 V	E	1.62	2.06	0.63	0.30
22 V	M	2.43	2.54	0.25	0.88
22 V	E	2.25	2.53	6.03	0.17
37 H	M	1.16	1.39	0.67	0.43
37 H	E	1.11	1.38	0.70	0.41
37 V	M	-0.36	-0.37	0.33	0.22
37 V	E	-0.38	-0.38	0.39	0.24
91 H	M	-0.15	0.04	0.96	1.02
91 H	E	-0.19	-0.03	1.27	0.94
91 V	M	-0.46	-0.37	0.71	0.59
91 V	E	-0.49	-0.37	1.08	0.54

Table 15: Average Probability distribution of differences for land and ocean over the four periods recorded for EASE2_S.

channel	pass	land mean	ocean mean	land std	ocean std
19 H	M	1.41	1.72	2.17	1.81
19 H	E	1.44	1.87	3.35	6.89
19 V	M	1.52	1.98	2.37	3.53
19 V	E	1.53	1.92	2.46	3.84
22 V	M	2.48	2.54	2.09	1.08
22 V	E	2.37	2.60	11.27	3.05
37 H	M	1.15	1.39	1.34	0.99
37 H	E	1.11	1.39	1.41	1.00
37 V	M	-0.37	-0.37	0.67	0.51
37 V	E	-0.38	-0.38	0.79	0.54
91 H	M	-0.14	-0.02	1.94	2.20
91 H	E	-0.18	0.01	2.51	2.04
91 V	M	-0.38	-0.32	3.30	3.10
91 V	E	-0.41	-0.28	3.36	3.67

Figure 1: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H ascending pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Overlapping land and ocean difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 2: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H ascending pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 3: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H ltod descending pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics for land and ocean separately (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 4: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V ascending pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 5: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V descending pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 6: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 7: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 8: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 9: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 10: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 11: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 12: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 13: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 14: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 15: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 16: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 17: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 18: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 19: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 20: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 21: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 22: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 23: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 24: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 25: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 26: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 27: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 28: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 29: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 30: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 31: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 32: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 33: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 34: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 35: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 36: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 37: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 38: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 39: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 40: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 41: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 42: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 43: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 44: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 45: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 46: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 47: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 48: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 49: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 50: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 51: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 52: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 53: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 54: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 55: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 56: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V ltod A. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 57: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V ltod D. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

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Land mean: 1.44 std: 0.65
Ocean mean: 1.71 std: 0.60

Figure 58: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 59: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 60: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 61: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 62: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 63: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 64: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 65: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 66: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 67: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 68: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 69: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 70: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 71: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 72: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 73: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 74: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 75: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 76: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 77: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 78: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 79: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 80: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 81: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 82: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 83: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 84: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 85: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 86: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 87: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 88: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 89: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 90: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 91: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 92: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 93: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 94: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 95: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 96: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 97: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 98: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 99: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 100: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 101: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 102: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 103: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 104: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 105: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 106: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 107: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 108: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 109: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 110: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 111: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 112: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 113: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

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Figure 114: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 115: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H ltod evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 116: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 117: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 118: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 119: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 120: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 121: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 122: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 123: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 124: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 125: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 126: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 127: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 1. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 1-10.

Figure 128: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 129: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 130: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 131: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 132: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 133: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 134: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 135: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 136: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 137: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 138: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 139: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 140: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 141: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 101. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 101-110.

Figure 142: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 143: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 144: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 145: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 146: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 147: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 148: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 149: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 150: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 151: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 152: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 153: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 154: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 155: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 201. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 201-210.

Figure 156: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 157: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19H evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 158: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 159: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 19V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 160: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 161: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 22V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 162: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 163: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37H evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 164: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 165: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 37V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 166: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 167: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91H evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 168: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V morning pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.

Figure 169: SSMIS difference analysis for year 2019, channel 91V evening pass. (a) Difference image (I/FCDR-L1C) for day 301. (b) Difference statistics (I/FCDR-L1C) for days 301-310.